

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

Response of Sweet Corn Growth to Soil Fertilization with Sulfur, NPK Levels and Spraying of Ascorbic Acid

Ali Hussein Jasim and Mohammad Raheem Hariz

Field Crops Department, Agriculture College, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to AHJ (email: ajasim11@gmail.com)

Received:

2023/03/07

Accepted:

2023/04/20

Published:

2023/07/03

Abstract

The experiment was carried out in Abu Gharaq area, 10 km west of Hilla city, Iraq during the autumn season of 2018 in silt clay soil to study the effect of foam sulfur addition (0 and 20 Kg.ha⁻¹), NPK fertilizer (20:20:20) at levels of 0, 75 and 150 Kg.ha⁻¹, ascorbic acid spraying at concentrations of (0, 25 and 50 mg.L⁻¹) and their interactions on growth of sweet corn. A randomized complete block design with three replications was used. The results showed that the addition of (20 Kg.ha⁻¹) foam sulfur caused a significant increase in plant height (125.9 cm), plant leaf number (12.19), plant leaf area (4206 cm²), chlorophyll (60.4 SPAD), leaf content of N, P and K (15.49, 2.854 and 19.66 mg.g⁻¹) respectively. Increasing the level of NPK up to (150 Kg.ha⁻¹) significantly caused an increase in plant height (126.8 cm), plant leaf number (12.06), plant leaf area (4258 cm²), chlorophyll (61.7 SPAD), leaf content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (15.63, 2.88 and 19.96 mg.g⁻¹) respectively. Spraying ascorbic acid up to (50 mg.L⁻¹) significantly increased plant leaf area (4208), and chlorophyll leaf content (59.2). The interactions between the factors caused a significant effect on most traits.

Keywords: Ascorbic acid; Foam sulfur; NPK fertilizer; Sweet corn

Introduction

Sweet corn (*Zea mays. Saccharata* Sturt) is one of the maize groups, but it is a newly introduced crop to be cultivated in Iraq (Jasim and Arat, 2021). Sulfur is used as a reformer for alkaline calcareous soil due to its oxidization to sulfuric acid which then increases the solubility of soil lime and reduces the soil pH which positively affects the availability of many nutrients in the soil (Al-Ezzawi, 2006). Sulfur is an essential nutrient for the formation of protein and amino acids as well as it plays a vital role in the composition of chlorophyll without entering the chlorophyll structure (Ali et al., 2014). It had a positive effect on increasing maize growth and nutrient uptake (Mahal et al., 2022). Adding essential mineral fertilizers, especially NPK is necessary to increase the growth and yield of plants, and its availability is important to supply the nutrient needs of maize plants (Sudding et al., 2021; Al-Gym and Al-Asady, 2020; Sebetha and Mashele, 2019; and Jasim et al., 2016). Ascorbic acid is an antioxidant compound and plays various roles in many physiological processes in plant growth (Pignocchi and Foyer, 2003; Smirnoff and Wheeler, 2000), enhances plant growth and improves sweet corn tolerance (Kotb et al., 2021; Ghassemi et al., 2020). This study aimed to determine the effect of foam sulfur, NPK (20-20-20), ascorbic acid and their interactions on the growth of sweet corn.

Materials and Methods

A factorial experiment was conducted in Babylon, Iraq at 32.52 North latitude and 44.37 East longitudes, in the autumn season of 2018 to study the influence of foam sulfur (0 and 20 kg.ha⁻¹), NPK (0, 75, and 150 Kg.ha⁻¹) and ascorbic acid levels (0, 25 and 50 mg.L⁻¹) on the growth of sweet corn in silt clay loam soil (Table 1).

A randomized complete block design with three replications was used. The seeds were planted on August 16, 2018 (Jasim and Alsaedi, 2018) on both sides of the ridges (100 cm) at 25 cm between plants. The experiment contained 54 experimental units (3x3 m for each one). Loam sulfur was added to the soil preparation according to treatments. NPK fertilizer was added in lines below plant line 10 cm (separated in two parts at the 8 and 12 leaf stages and the ascorbic acid was sprayed at the 8 and 12 leaf stages. At maturity (November 20), 10 plants from inner lines were assessed to calculate plant height, plant leaves number, plant leaf area, and leaf chlorophyll (SPAD). At flowering, 5 leaves from each experimental unit were taken to determine N, P and K content. Genstat-12 was used to analyze the data and the means were compared by LSD 0.05.

Table 1. Some soil physical and chemical characteristics before planting

The character		Value	The character	Value	
pH		7.5	Soil mixture	sand	186 mg kg ⁻¹
ECe		2.91 dSc m ⁻¹		silt	339 mg kg ⁻¹
				clay	475 mg kg ⁻¹
Available	N	8.41 mg kg ⁻¹	Soil texture		Silt clay soil
	P	10.02 mg kg ⁻¹			
	K	191.0 mg kg ⁻¹			

Results and discussion

Table (2) shows that the addition of sulfur caused a significant effect on increasing the plant height to 125.9 cm compared to the control treatment (117.3 cm). This increase may be due to the role of sulfur in plant nutrition and its entry into many vital processes within the plant, causing an increase in cell division and elongation, and this result is consistent with Tiwari et al. (2022); Elfahdawi and Ali (2020). NPK fertilizers caused a significant effect on plant height and the level of 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ gave the highest average of 126.8 cm, compared to the control treatment (116.6 cm). This increase may be due to the availability and absorption of these nutrients, as nitrogen has a positive effect on the activity of meristem tissues, cell division, and the biosynthesis of amino acids, including tryptophan, the source of IAA, which plays a role in cell division (Alasady and Jasim, 2019). Also, phosphorus plays a role in activating the process of cell division due to its entry into the formation of many energy-rich compounds, increasing cell division and elongation. These results are in line with Chakraborty et al. (2020), and Al-Gym and Al-Asady (2020). All the interactions between the factors caused a significant effect on this trait, and adding 20 kg ha⁻¹ foamy sulfur + 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ NPK + 50 mg.L⁻¹ ascorbic acid gave the highest plant height (130.6 cm), compared to the control treatment (109.3 cm).

Table 2. Effect of sulfur, NPK fertilizer levels and ascorbic acid levels on plant height (cm)

Sulfur	NPK (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Ascorbic acid (mg L ⁻¹)			Sulfur X NPK	Mean of NPK	Mean of sulfur
		0	25	50			
0	0	109.3	110.0	114.0	111.1	116.6	117.3
	75	111.7	117.5	121.1	116.8	121.3	
	50	120.0	125.9	126.0	123.9	126.8	
20	0	119.0	123.5	124.0	122.2		125.9
	75	120.4	127.7	129.5	125.8		
	150	128.4	129.9	130.6	129.6		
LSD _{0.05}		17.84			10.30	7.28	5.95
Sulfur	0	113.7	117.8	120.4			
	20	122.6	127.0	128.0			
LSD _{0.05}		10.30					
NPK	0	114.1	116.7	119.0			
	75	116.1	122.6	125.3			
	150	124.1	127.9	128.3			
LSD _{0.05}		12.62					
Mean of ascorbic		118.1	122.4	124.2			
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.					

Table (3) showed that sulfur caused a significant effect on increasing plant leaves number, to 12.19 compared to the control treatment (11.56 leaves). This increase may be due to S in increasing many plant vital processes as well as increasing the soil acidity, which facilitates the solubility and readiness of other nutrients and their absorption by the plant, which is positively reflected in this characteristic. This result is consistent with Tiwari et al. (2022), and Jasim and Ghani (2015). Plant leaf number was significantly affected by adding NPK and the level of 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ gave the highest number (12.06), compared to the control treatment (11.33). This result may be attributed to an increase in the readiness of N, P and K elements in the soil solution and their absorption by plant roots, which leads to an increase in cell division and growth. This result is in line with Chakraborty et al. (2020), Al-Gym and Al-Asady (2020); Sebetha and Mashele (2019). The interaction between S and NPK caused a significant effect, and the treatment of 20 Kg.ha⁻¹ sulfur + 75 Kg.ha⁻¹ NPK gave the highest number (12.30), compared to the control treatment (11.28). The interaction between S and ascorbic acid caused a significant effect and adding 20 Kg.ha⁻¹ sulfur + 50 mg.L⁻¹ ascorbic acid gave the highest number (12.30) compared to the control treatment (11.22).

Table 3. Effect of sulfur, NPK fertilizer levels and ascorbic acid levels on plant leaf number

Sulfur	NPK (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Ascorbic acid (mg L ⁻¹)			Sulfur X NPK	Mean of NPK	Mean of sulfur
		0	25	50			
0	0	11.03	11.27	11.44	11.28	11.33	11.56
	75	11.47	11.23	11.50	11.40	11.85	
	150	11.17	12.03	12.10	11.86	12.06	
20	0	11.93	12.05	12.16	12.04		12.19
	75	12.17	12.31	12.35	12.30		
	150	12.09	12.36	12.39	12.21		
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.			0.971	0.687	0.561
sulfur	0	11.22	11.51	11.79			
	20	12.16	12.10	12.30			
LSD _{0.05}		0.971					
NPK	0	11.48	11.65	11.83			
	75	11.92	11.70	11.93			
	150	11.67	12.07	12.38			
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.					
Mean of ascorbic		11.34	11.81	12.02			
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.					

Table (4) shows that adding sulfur caused a significant increase in plant leaves area to 4206 cm² compared to the control treatment (3896 cm²). This may be due to the role of sulfur in the formation of many compounds, especially protein compounds, as well as reducing soil pH, which leads to an increase in the readiness of nutrients, thus improving plant growth and development which is reflected in the leaf area. This result is consistent with Elfahdawi et al. (2020) and Padma et al. (2018). NPK fertilizer levels affected plant leaf area and adding 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ NPK gave the highest average of 4258 cm², compared to the control treatment (3848 cm²). This may be due to increasing their uptake by the plant, and their effect on cell division and expansion. This result is in line with Chakraborty et al. (2020); Hasan et al. (2020), Sebetha and Mashele (2019). Ascorbic acid caused a significant increase in plant leaf area, and the concentration of 50 mg.L⁻¹ gave the highest average leaf area (4208 cm²) compared to the control treatment (3989 cm²). This may be due to the role of ascorbic as a catalyst and companion for many enzymes, as well as its role in the biosynthesis of several hormones, including gibberellins, which leads to cell expansion, elongation, and division, which is reflected in plant leaf area. This result agrees with Al-Freeh et al. (2020) and Mohammed et al. (2019). The interaction between the factors caused a significant effect and adding 20 Kg.ha⁻¹ sulfur + 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ NPK + 50 mg.L⁻¹ ascorbic acid gave the highest leaf area (4371 cm²), compared to the control treatment (3369 cm²).

Table (5) showed that adding sulfur caused a significant increase in leaf chlorophyll content to 60.4 compared to the control treatment (53.0). This may be attributed to the role of sulfur in decreasing the soil pH, which leads to an increase in elements solubility and readiness, and their absorption,

which reflected positively on plant growth and leaf chlorophyll content. This result agreed with Al-Salami et al. (2021). The chlorophyll was significantly increased by adding NPK, and the level of 150 kg/ha gave the highest average of 61.7 compared to the control treatment (52.1). This may be attributed to the availability and absorption of NPK and their effect, as nitrogen has a positive effect on the formation of the chlorophyll molecule. This result was agreed with Al-Gym and Al-Asady (2020), Hasan et al. (2020), and Jasim and Kateb (2017). The ascorbic acid caused a significant effect on increasing the chlorophyll, and spraying 50 mg.L⁻¹, gave the highest chlorophyll content of 59.2 compared to the control treatment, (53.7). This is consistent with Dogru and Yprlak (2020); Sebetha and Mashele (2019). The interactions between the factors caused a significant effect and adding 20 Kg.ha⁻¹ sulfur + 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ NPK + 50 mg.L⁻¹ ascorbic acid gave the highest of 66.0, compared to the control treatment (48.0).

Table 4. Effect of sulfur, NPK fertilizer levels and ascorbic acid levels on plant leaf area (cm²)

Sulfur	NPK (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Ascorbic acid (mg L ⁻¹)			Sulfur X NPK	Mean of NPK	Mean of sulfur
		0	25	50			
0	0	3369	3818	3597	3595	3848	3896
	75	3928	3632	4080	3880	4047	
	150	4262	4186	4187	4212	4258	
20	0	4000	4150	4151	4101		4206
	75	4152	4226	4264	4214		
	150	4227	4313	4371	4304		
LSD _{0.05}		484.5			279.7	197.8	161.5
Sulfur	0	3853	3879	3955			
	20	4126	4230	4262			
LSD _{0.05}		279.7					
NPK	0	3685	3984	3874			
	75	4039	3929	4172			
	150	4244	4250	4279			
LSD _{0.05}		342.6					
Mean of ascorbic		3989	4054	4208			
LSD _{0.05}		197.8					

Table 5. Effect of sulfur, NPK fertilizer levels and ascorbic acid levels on chlorophyll (SPAD)

Sulfur	NPK (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Ascorbic acid (mg L ⁻¹)			Sulfur X NPK	Mean of NPK	Mean of sulfur
		0	25	50			
0	0	48.0	49.9	49.9	49.3	52.1	53.0
	75	50.3	50.6	54.7	51.9	56.5	
	150	52.6	59.3	62.0	58.0	61.7	
20	0	50.9	56.3	57.4	54.9		60.4
	75	55.5	62.3	65.3	61.1		
	150	64.8	65.4	66.0	65.4		
LSD _{0.05}		13.14			7.59	5.36	4.36
Sulfur	0	50.3	53.3	55.7			
	20	57.1	61.3	62.9			
LSD _{0.05}		7.59					
NPK	0	49.5	52.9	53.1			
	75	53.7	56.5	60.0			
	150	58.7	62.6	64.0			
LSD _{0.05}		9.29					
Mean of ascorbic		53.7	57.3	59.2			
LSD _{0.05}		5.36					

Table (6) showed that adding sulfur caused a significant increase of N content to 15.49 mg/g, compared to the control treatment (14.42 mg/g). This result may be attributed to the fact that sulfur improved plant growth and also led to increasing N available (Elfahdawi et al., 2020), and its absorption, which reflected positively in increasing leaf N content. This result agrees with Jaliya

et al. (2012). Adding NPK fertilizer caused a significant increase in N content and the level of 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ achieved the highest average of 15.63 mg/g, compared to the control treatment (14.26 mg/g). This result was attributed to the increase in N availability and absorption by the plant. This result is consistent with Sofyan et al. (2021); Canatoy and Daquiado (2021). The interaction between the factors caused a significant increase in N content and the highest average (16.08 mg/g) was achieved by adding 20 Kg.ha⁻¹ foam sulfur + 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ NPK + 50 mg.L⁻¹ ascorbic acid compared to 12.31 mg/g at control treatment.

Table 6. Effect of sulfur, NPK fertilizer levels and ascorbic acid levels on N content (mg.g⁻¹)

Sulfur	NPK (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Ascorbic acid (mg L ⁻¹)			Sulfur X NPK	Mean of NPK	Mean of sulfur
		0	25	50			
0	0	12.31	14.21	13.97	13.49	14.26	14.42
	75	14.17	14.59	14.79	14.52	14.97	
	50	14.74	15.41	15.56	15.23	15.63	
20	0	14.76	15.14	15.20	15.03		15.49
	75	14.75	15.59	15.93	15.42		
	150	15.98	16.02	16.08	16.03		
LSD _{0.05}		3.678			1.461	1.043	1.035
Sulfur	0	13.74	14.75	14.77			
	20	15.16	15.58	15.74			
LSD _{0.05}		1.461					
NPK	0	13.53	14.67	14.58			
	75	14.46	15.09	15.35			
	150	15.36	15.71	15.82			
LSD _{0.05}		2.287					
Mean of ascorbic		14.45	15.16	15.26			
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.					

Table (7) showed that the addition of sulfur achieved a significant increase in P content to 2.854 mg/g, compared to the control treatment (2.514 mg/g). This result may be attributed to the decrease in the soil pH, thus dissolving phosphorus, increasing its availability (Elfahdawi et al., 2020), and its absorption by the plant. This result agreed with Rahman et al. (2011). Adding NPK caused a significant increase, and the level of 150 and 75 Kg.ha⁻¹ achieved the highest content of 2.880 and 2.707 mg/g, respectively, compared to 2.466 mg/g at the control treatment. This result may be due to the increase in the readiness of phosphorus in the soil solution, and its absorption by the plant.

Table 7. Effect of sulfur, NPK fertilizer levels and ascorbic acid levels on P content (mg.g⁻¹)

Sulfur	NPK (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Ascorbic acid (mg L ⁻¹)			Sulfur X NPK	Mean of NPK	Mean of sulfur
		0	25	50			
0	0	2.253	2.393	2.413	2.377	2.466	2.514
	75	2.377	2.570	2.650	2.577	2.707	
	50	2.620	2.630	2.653	2.634	2.880	
20	0	2.463	2.447	2.600	2.556		2.854
	75	2.673	3.077	3.120	2.881		
	150	3.080	3.147	3.150	3.126		
LSD _{0.05}		0.677			0.3646	0.2578	0.2105
Sulfur	0	2.417	2.554	2.572			
	20	2.640	2.941	2.981			
LSD _{0.05}		0.3646					
NPK	0	2.323	2.412	2.532			
	75	2.543	2.823	2.885			
	150	2.850	2.888	2.902			
LSD _{0.05}		0.4465					
Mean of ascorbic		2.528	2.748	2.777			
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.					

This result agreed with Sofyan et al. (2021); Canatoy and Daquiado (2021), Al-Gym and Al-Asady (2020). The interaction between the factors caused a significant increase in P content and adding 20 Kg.ha⁻¹ sulfur + 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ NPK + 50 mg/L ascorbic acid achieved the highest leaf content (3.150 mg/g) compared to 2.253 mg/g at control treatment.

Table (8) showed that the addition of sulfur caused a significant increase of K content to 19.66 mg/g, compared to the control treatment (18.54 mg/g). This may be attributed to the role of sulfur in decreasing soil pH value which is reflected in increasing the availability of K (Elfahdawi et al., 2020) and its absorption. This result agreed with Jeet et al. (2012). NPK adding caused a significant increase, and the level of 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ achieved the highest average of 19.96 mg/g, compared to 18.47 mg/g at the control treatment. This result may be attributed to the role of NPK in increasing root spread and expansion and increasing K availability and its absorption by the plant. This result agreed with Sofyan et al. (2021); Canatoy and Daquiado (2021); Al-Gym and Al-Asady (2020). The interaction between foamy sulfur and NPK caused a significant increase and adding 20 Kg.ha⁻¹ sulfur + 150 Kg.ha⁻¹ NPK achieved the highest K content (20.44 mg/g) compared to 17.79 mg/g at the control treatment.

Table 8. Effect of sulfur, NPK fertilizer levels, and ascorbic acid levels on K content (mg.g⁻¹)

sulfur	NPK (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Ascorbic acid (mg L ⁻¹)			Sulfur X NPK	Mean of NPK	Mean of sulfur
		0	25	50			
0	0	17.69	17.77	17.92	17.79	18.47	18.54
	75	17.91	18.21	18.94	18.35	18.87	
	150	18.90	19.64	19.90	19.48	19.96	
20	0	18.89	19.16	18.28	19.14		19.66
	75	18.23	19.61	19.38	19.39		
	150	20.34	20.46	20.51	20.44		
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.			2.458	1.154	1.044
Sulfur	0	18.17	18.54	18.92			
	20	19.17	19.74	20.06			
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.					
NPK	0	18.09	18.46	18.65			
	75	18.29	18.91	19.61			
	150	19.62	20.05	20.21			
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.					
Mean of ascorbic		18.67	19.14	19.49			
LSD _{0.05}		n.s.					

Conclusion

From this experiment, it is clear that adding sulfur as an essential element to improve soil pH was active in enhancing the growth of sweet corn plants grown in soil tending to alkaline and increasing leaf content of N, P, and K by increasing the readiness of nutrients. Also, compound chemical fertilizer NPK (20-20-20) caused an increase in all plant growth indicators and leaf NPK content by increasing the availability of these elements. Ascorbic acid was sprayed as an antioxidant compound to increase the plant's resistance to reactive oxygen species and improve growth. Spraying ascorbic acid increased plant leaf area and leaf chlorophyll content.

References

- Alasady MH and Jasim AH (2019) Plant Hormones and Their Physiological Effects. Al-Warith Press, Iraq.
- Al-Ezzawi SSJ (2006) Efficiency effect of agriculture sulfur and ammonium sulfate in availability and behavior of phosphorus of rock phosphate and on some nutrients uptake and corn growth. A thesis, College of Agriculture, University of Baghdad. 156p.
- Ali NS, Rahi HS and Shaker AA (2014) Soil fertility. Scientific Books, Baghdad, Iraq. 307p.
- Al-Freeh LM, Alshummary AM and Alabdulla SA (2020) Effect of foliar spray with ascorbic acid on two maize cultivars grown under saline soil. International Journal Agriculture and Statistic Science, 16(1): 2073-2078.

Al-Gym AJK and Al-Asady, MHS (2020) Effect of the method and level of adding NPK nanoparticles and mineral fertilizers on the growth and yield of yellow corn and the content of mineral nutrient of some plant parts. *Plant Archives*, 20 (1): 38-43.

Al-Salami AS, Mohson KH and Desher MA (2021) Effect of agriculture sulfur fertilizer levels on growth, and yield of wheat. *Plant Archives*, 21 (1): 1102-1107.

Canatoy RC and Daquiado NP (2021) Fertilization influence on biomass yield and nutrient uptake of sweet corn in potentially hard setting soil under no tillage. *Bulletin of the National Research Centre*, 45:61 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42269-021-00526-w>.

Chakraborty S, Das S, Mahanty A, et al. (2020) Effect of integrated nutrient management on baby corn on baby corn under Gangetic Alluvial land after rice. *Indian Agriculture*, 64(3&4):83-88.

Dogru A and Torlak E (2020) Effects of exogenous ascorbic acid application in maize plants under salt stress. *Yüzüncü Yıl University Journal Agriculture Science*, 30:928-936.

Elfahdawi WAT, Ahmed F and Cheyed SH (2020) Effect of Agricultural Sulfur on Availability of NPK in Soil, Growth and Yield of Corn (*Zea mays* L.). *Indian Journal Ecology*, (2020) 47 Special Issue (12): 200-205.

Ghassemi A, Farzaneh S and Moharramnejad S (2020) Impact of ascorbic acid on seed yield and its components in sweet corn (*Zea mays* L.) under drought stress. *Journal of Plant Physiology and Breeding*, 10(1): 41-49.

Hasan S, Nompo S, Mujnisa A, et al. (2020) The increase of corn crop productivity through NPK fertilizer addition in Dyland. *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 492 (2020) 012007.

Jaliya MM, Chiezey UF, Tanimu B, et al. (2012) Effects of Nitrogen and sulfur fertilizers on nitrogen content in soil, ear leaf, flag leaf and grain of QPM maize varieties at Samaru Zaria. *Journal Agriculture Science*, 4:217-222.

Jasim AH and Ghani MM (2015) The response of maize, *Zea mays* ssp. *evarta* L. for urea-sulfur fertilizer and urea spraying. *Euphrates Journal Agriculture Science*, 7 (4): 147-153.

Jasim AH and Kateb IM (2017) Vegetative growth response of four genotypes of maize for supplemental nitrogen fertilizer levels. *Karbala University Science Journal*, 15(1):171-177.

Jasim AH and Al- Saeedi MBH (2018) Effect of planting dates and additional nitrogen fertilizer on some yield traits of sweet corn. *Res. on Crops*, 19 (4): 604- 608.

Jasim AH, and Arat AA (2021) The effect of planting dates, plant density, and silicon spraying on the growth and yield of sweet corn. *South Asian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 1(1): 38-42.

Jasim AH, Atta KN, Hasson KM, et al (2016) Effect of foliar application with some treatments to avoid stress environments on spring planting of maize (*Zea mayze* L.). *Mesopotamia Environment Journal*, Special Issue A.;115-123.

Jeet S, Singh JP, Kumar R, et al. (2012) Effect of nitrogen and sulfur levels on yield, economic and quality of QPM hybrid under dry land condition of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. *Journal Agriculture Science*, 4:31-38.

Kotb MA, Mohammed AA, El-Sayed MM, et al. (2021) Effect of interaction between water stress and foliar application by ascorbic acid or micronutrients on maize productivity and irrigation water use efficiency. *Zagazig Journal Agriculture Research*, 48 (3):643-658.

Mahal NK, Sawyer JE, Iqbal J, et al. (2022) Role of sulfur mineralization and fertilizer source in corn and soybean production systems. *Soil Science Society of American Journal*, 86, 1058–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1002/saj2.20417>.

Mohammed LS, Abdulla KI and Mustafa AS (2019) Effect of ascorbic acid concentration and harvesting date on growth and yield of three corn varieties (*Zea mays* L.). *Plant Archives*, 19(2): 2390-2395.

Padma PV, Vidyasagar GE, Suresh P, et al. (2018) Effect of Different Sources and Levels of Sulphur on Growth and Yield of Maize (*Zea mays* L.). *International Journal Current Microbiological Applied Science*, 7(8): 1548-1559.

Pignocchi C, and Foyer CH (2003) Apoplastic ascorbate metabolism and its role in the regulation of cell signaling. *Current Opinion Plant Biology*, 6: 379-389.

Rahman MM, Soaud AA, Al Darwish FH, et al. (2011) Effects of sulfur and nitrogen on nutrients uptake of corn using acidified water. *African Journal Biotechnology*, 10(42): 8275-828.

Sebetha ET, and Mashele LV (2019) The growth performance of sweet corn under the influence of animal manure, NPK and soil type. *Indian J. Agric. Res.*, 53(6): 718-722.

Smirnov N and Wheeler GL (2000) Ascorbic Acid in Plants: Biosynthesis and Function. *Critical Reviews in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*. 35 (4) : 291-314.

Sofyan ET, Sara DS and Machfud Y (2021) The effect of organic and inorganic fertilizer applications on N, P-uptake, K-uptake and yield of sweet corn (*Zea mays saccharata* Sturt). *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 393, 012021, doi:10.1088/1755-1315/393/1/012021.

Sudding AF, Ashri M, Rauf AW, et al. (2021) The effect of NPK 15-15-6-4 compound fertilizer on corn growth and yield. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environmental Science*. 911 012047.

Tiwari DK, Chaturvedi DP and Singh T (2022) Effect of nitrogen and sulfur levels on growth, yield and quality of maize (*Zea mays* L.). *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 11(1): 418-422.

Author Contributions

AHJ and MRH conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Funding

There is no funding source for the present study.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. Visit for more details <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Citation: Jasim AH and Hariz MR (2023) Response of Sweet Corn Growth to Soil Fertilization with Sulfur, NPK Levels and Spraying of Ascorbic Acid. *Environ Sci Arch* 2(2):114-121.